

OPINION ESSAY TIPS AND TRICKS

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ANNOTATION

The article emphasizes the differences of IELTS essays and especially outlines the structure of an opinion essay. To illustrate, it is identified that understanding the question which was expressed in Writing task 2 should be clearly understood by the candidate in order to write properly and avoid being out of topic. Moreover, the structure of introduction, main part and conclusion: how many parts they include and what kind of sentences are used to write them are described by means of examples.

Key words: *opinion essays, discussion essay, topic sentence, thesis statement, outline statement, main supportive sentence, and detailed sentence.*

It is argued that any type of IELTS essays requires opinion therefore it is slightly awkward to call an opinion essay. However each type acquires its own structure and purpose of writing. According to the purpose, although all of them contain an opinion they are known as different names such as opinion essay, discussion essay, advantage-disadvantage or problem solving essays. Among them opinion and discussion essays have striking resemblance in their structure consequently, majority candidates make mistakes in differences between an opinion and discussion essay while writing the essay. Below the differences between these two types and their layouts are described: Which is a discussion essay, and which is the opinion essay?

A-Because of the increased demand for oil, protected areas should be opened up to access more resources. To what extent do you agree?

B-Because of increased demand for oil, some believe that protected areas must be opened to access more resources, while others believe that we must protect areas and find other sources of energy. Discuss both views and give your own opinion.

A-discussion essay; B-Opinion essay

Firstly, discussion essays include two opposite opinions. Look for these words: 'some people...', 'other people...'

Linking words to highlight the contrast: 'while', 'whereas', or 'whilst'

On the contrary, Opinion essay's task is to write personal opinion about statement. Look for these expressions: To what extent do you agree or disagree or Do you agree or disagree?

Secondly, Discussion essay layout is described the followings:

- ✓ unlike an opinion essay, you shouldn't put your thesis statement in the introduction.
- ✓ It is much better to brainstorm ideas for both sides equally. Each side of the argument has an equal paragraph
- ✓ Then give your opinion in the conclusion.

In opinion essay unlike discussion essays, you put your thesis in the introduction paragraph.

It is your goal to persuade the reader. Moreover, there are three layouts you can choose because you are asked; how much do you agree or disagree—fully, partially, fully disagree

In the following stage we shall observe an opinion essay analyze with sample written by IELTS examiners.

Task: A big salary is much more important than job satisfaction. Do you agree or disagree?

Give reasons for your answer and include any relevant examples from your own knowledge or experience. Write at least 250 words. It is known from the task question that it is an opinion essay. Therefore, It is good choice to start with essay structure:

Opinion essay structure

1. Introduction

paraphrase the question

give your opinion

state two supporting reasons

2. Main paragraph 1.

topic sentence—outline 1st reason for supporting this view

Explanation—explain this idea

Example

3. Main paragraph 2.

topic sentence—outline 1st reason for supporting this view

Explanation—explain this idea

Example

4. Conclusion

Summarise opinion and key reasons

Likewise, it is valued to generate ideas about the statement which was outlined as a question. In this stage candidate ought to concentrate on the ideas which appeared in their mind and choose the most two informative ideas which can be explained by details because it is vitally important to persuade the reader. The following ideas can be written:

High salary jobs are generally more stressful

Stress leads to ill health, both mental and physical

40 hours a week at work—

A third of a day

Money does not bring happiness

Better quality of life

Sense of fulfillment

Less stressed—

Healthier and happier

Having brainstormed ideas, it is advised to choose at least two of them to illustrate during the essay.

Idea 1—High-salary jobs are generally more stressful and can lead to ill health

Idea 2— Job satisfaction gives a sense of fulfillment.

Moreover, writer ought to take advantage of synonyms of expressed words in the question in order to achieve satisfactory scores for the vocabulary.

e.g. satisfaction—fulfillment, achievement, sense of accomplishment, content, sense of well being;

salary—income, wages, pay, earnings; important— significant, valued, has more meaning job— work, employment, position.

A good introduction has a simple 3 part structure: paraphrased sentence, thesis statement, outline statement.

e.g. It is argued that earning lots of money has more significance to people than being content in their work. (**paraphrased sentence**). This essay totally disagrees with the statement or This essay completely agrees with that statement (**thesis statement**). I believe that people are increasingly concerned about the risk of stress-related ill-health frequently experienced by people in highly paid positions and they care more about feeling fulfilled at work (**outlined statement**).

In introduction 3 key functions should be expressed:

- 1) It shows the examiner that you understand the question.
- 2) It acts as a guide to the examiner as to what your essay is about
- 3) It also helps to keep you focused and on track as you write

In main body paragraph structure each idea might be outlined in one paragraph:

Main part 1 – concerns about the risk of stress related ill-health

Main part 2 – a sense of fulfillment at work.

Each paragraph contains the following sentences concerned with ideas:

Topic sentence (thesis statement)

Explanation (main supportive sentence)

Example (detailed sentence)

Main body paragraph 1

Employees who earn a large income are generally under significantly mental and emotional pressure to perform well and achieve targets. This causes many individuals to suffer high levels of stress which can result in mental health problems. This happened to my uncle. He used to boast about his huge salary but the boss kept increasing his sales targets and in the end, the stress became too great and he had a nervous breakdown. Now he regrets being driven by the money.

Main body paragraph 2

Having a job at that they enjoy doing, and in which they feel valued, is a major concern for most of the modern workforce. A significant number of people are giving up well-paid positions to do jobs which pays less but that they find more enjoyable and less stressful. I am an example of this myself. A year ago I gave up the teaching profession because the workload had become too great and am now a gardener. I feel really fulfilled in this work and am much more relaxed and happy even though I earn far less money.

Opinion essay conclusion regularly summarizes the main points by restating your opinion:

(Introduction).It is argued that earning lots of money has more significance to people than being content in their work. This essay totally disagrees with that statement. I believe that people are increasingly concerned about the risk of stress related ill health frequently experienced by people in highly paid positions and they care more about feeling fulfilled at work.

(Conclusion)In conclusion, for a high percentage of the population, earning a substantial wage is less important than job satisfaction because of the negative effects of work-related stress and the desire to feel happy and fulfilled at work.

To sum up, candidates should know the structure of any essay that they intend to write and to identify the type particularly, they should completely understand the question. Knowing the strategies mentioned above contribute to write properly an opinion essay.

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